

CHEMICAL EXAMINATION OF THE OIL FROM THE SEEDS OF *SANTALUM ALBUM* (LINN).*

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Physical and chemical constants of various constituents of the oil from the seeds of *Santalum album* have been determined. The solid has been found to consist of one component with a trace of palmitic acid and from analysis it is considered to be a triolefinic compound of the formula $C_{18}H_{32}O_2$.

Sandal seeds contain about 50% of a valuable highly viscous fatty oil and the problem of its large scale expression from seeds has been recently solved by Mr. Gopalaswamy Reddy of New Oil Mills, Bangalore. The chief difficulty in large scale production consists in the high cost of the collection of the seeds. The oil itself has been the subject of several preliminary investigations (K.A.N. Rao *et al*, *Quarterly J. of the Mysore Forest Dept.*, 1934, p. 7; Iyer, *Analyst*, 1935, 60 319; Sreenivasaya and Narayana, *J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1936, 19A, 1). In view of the possibilities of the commercial exploitation of the oil, a detailed investigation of the various constituents was undertaken with the following results.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The oil was prepared by the extraction of the seeds (oil content 44%) by means of petroleum ether (b.p. 60-70°). The following table gives the physical and chemical constants of the oil thus obtained and of the oil obtained by the expression of the seeds.

TABLE I.

	Extracted oil.	Expressed oil
Colour	Golden yellow	Dark brown
Specific gravity	0.9356 at 25°/25°	0.9346 at 27°/27°
Refractive index	1.4891 at 30°	1.4884 at 30°
Saponification value	176	176
Iodine (Hanus) ..	153	153
Thiocyanogen ..	151	—
Acid ..	29	44
Reichert-Meisel ..	0.9	0.8
Acetyl ..	22	25
Maleic anhydride ..	3.9	—
Unsaponifiable matter	8.8%	13%
Viscosity	243 at 50°/50°	

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The maximum absorption of oxygen by the extracted oil, when exposed in thin layers in an atmosphere of oxygen, was found to be 13%. On drying the oil was converted into an elastic film.

The oil was saponified by alcoholic potash when an elastic white sticky material separated out (5.2 g. from 100 g. of oil). This was removed by filtration through a thick cloth. The fatty acids were liberated from the soap solution and worked up in the usual manner.

TABLE II.

	Total fatty acids.	Solid acids.	Liquid acids.
Percentage	87.2	51	49
Mean M. W.	291	288.6	301.6
Iodine value (Hanus)	111	119.0	108
Resin acids	2.3%	—	—

Liquid Acids.—These were purified by the distillation of their methyl esters in vacuum and the liberated acids were examined by the method of oxidation (Lapworth and Mottram, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1628) and bromination (Lewkowitsch, "Chemical Technology and Analysis of Oils, Fats and Waxes", 6th Ed., Vol. I, 585). In the former case, only dihydroxystearic acid (m.p. 130°; M.W., 315.4) could be isolated. When the products of bromination were dissolved in cold petroleum ether a small amount (0.08 g. from 10 g. of liquid acids) of hexabromostearic acid (m.p. 183; M.W., 762) separated.

These results indicate that the liquid acids consist mainly of oleic acids together with a small amount of linolenic acid.

Solid Acids.—The acids obtained from the insoluble lead salts during the Twitchell separation were esterified with methyl alcohol and the esters (220 g.) were fractionally distilled at 1 mm. pressure.

TABLE III.

No. of fraction.	Range of temperature.	Weight of fraction.	Mean M. W. of acids from saponification value.
1	Up to 180°	0.5 g.	—
2	180-183°	140	275.8
3	183-188°	40	278.8
4	188-190°	8	274.7
5	190-194°	17	271.0
6 Residue and loss		9.5	—

From the first fraction a small amount (0.1 g.) of pure palmitic acid was isolated (m. p. 61°; M. W. 255), but no pure material could be obtained from the residue which was highly resinous.

Fractions 2-5 were very carefully refractionated at a pressure of 0.6 mm. Most of the material distilled over between 172-175° and only very small amounts were collected between 175-180° and above 180°. Here also there was considerable resinification.

TABLE IV.

	Range of fraction.	Mean M. W. of acids from saponification value.	Iodine value (Hanus).
A	172-175°	274.3	133
B	175-180°	275.3	133
C	Above 180°	278.4	131

The results indicate that the solid acids consist of one component with a trace of palmitic acid. The acid liberated from the refractionated esters solidified gradually and on recrystallisation from petroleum ether or methyl alcohol melted at 41-42°. (Found: C, 77.8, 77.8; H, 11.0, 11.0; M. W., 281, 281. $C_{18}H_{30}O_2$ requires C, 77.7; H, 10.8 per cent. and M. W., 278). It is very soluble in all the usual organic solvents and possesses a characteristic odour. Its *p*-phenylphenacyl ester melts at 56-57°.

Analysis indicated that the acid was a triolefinic compound of the formula $C_{18}H_{30}O_2$. Although iodine value obtained was 133 against 274 for a pure trienic acid of the formula $C_{18}H_{30}O_2$, it may be due to the difficulty of complete iodine addition. But when it was subjected to quantitative catalytic hydrogenation it took up 3.1 and 3.0 mols. of hydrogen and the product formed was found to be stearic acid (m. p. 69-70°; M. W., 286; m. p. of *p*-bromophenacyl ester, 90°). The thiocyanogen number of the pure acid was 130 and the maleic anhydride number, 8.4 (Ellis and Jones, *Analyst*, 1936, 61, 812). It did not give any crystallisable material on bromination carried out as with liquid acids. Attempts to prepare a crystallisable adduct with maleic anhydride (Kaufmann and Daltes, *Ber.*, 1936, 69, 2679) were also unsuccessful.

The acid was also found to be different from punicic acid (m. p. 44°, Toyama and Tsuchiya, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind. Japan*, 1935, 38, 182 B, 185 B;

Farmer and Henvel, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1809) since it could not be made to undergo photoisomerisation into β -elaeostearic acid. There is every indication that it is a new trienic acid and the name *santalbic acid* is proposed for it. A study of its constitution is in progress.

Unsaponifiable Matter.—A small amount of phytosterol (m. p. 131° ; m. p. of acetate, 118°) was isolated from the ether extract of the sodium soap.

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